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Urban public transport trends in five western international metropolises: A post-pandemic perspective

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Abstract: This study analyzes demand fluctuations in urban public transportation systems of São Paulo, New York, Paris, London, and Mexico City before and after the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020. We examined annual passenger data from 2017 to 2022. Pre-pandemic, São Paulo and London saw declining trends, while Paris, New York, and Mexico City remained relatively stable, with minor fluctuations. The pandemic caused a sharp drop in passengers in April and May 2020, followed by varying degrees of recovery. Paris had a robust recovery, São Paulo, London, and Mexico City recovered differently, and New York had a slower rebound. Subway and urban train systems showed stronger recoveries compared to urban buses. Overall, post-pandemic recovery was positive, with a gradual passenger increase each year but still below 2017 levels, indicating changed mobility habits.

Keywords: Urban public transport; Public transport data; Urban passenger movement; Analysis of trends in public transport; Covid-19

1. Contextualization

The Covid-19 Pandemic had a significant impact on the global economy in 2020, dropping the world's GDP by 4,5%, the American GDP by 3,4%, the Euro Zone's by 7,7%, and Brazil's by 4,1% [1]. These impacts directly affected the passenger transport sector, drastically reducing the number of passengers transported, affecting cities of all sizes, including large international metropolises such as São Paulo, London, Paris, New York and Mexico City. Due to their global importance and vast populations, these cities have felt the effects of both the initial reduction in passengers and their slow recovery.

At the start of the Covid-19 pandemic in March 2020, passenger volumes in global urban public transport systems plummeted by between 80% and 95%, with metro systems achieving partial recovery by July 2020. Recovery varied in different regions of the world, with Asia reaching around 70%, Europe around 50%, and the Americas between 20% and 30% of the previous volume [2, 3, 4].

A study in the United States, in April 2020, showed that public transport fell by 20% to 45% compared to February 2019. New York only transported around 15% of 2019's passengers, a situation that persisted until January 2021 [5]. In São Paulo, public transport reduced to 25% at the start of the pandemic and subsequently recovered to 58% in January 2021, compared to 2019.

Before the pandemic, public bus transport in Brazil was already in decline, with drops of 24% from 1994 to 2012 and 26% from 2013 to 2019 [6]. This trend of declining passengers is not exclusive to Brazil, as cities such as New York and London also lost

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significant numbers of passengers in 2018. These declines mainly affected urban bus systems, as subway systems gained passengers over time. with improvements in its services [7].

In this scenario of reduced use of public transport, several solutions are proposed, such as urban reorganization, increased home office, and encouraging the use of public transport, as ways to minimize the impact of the drop in passengers [8]. In the meantime, São Paulo City Hall began a survey of the origin and destination of municipal bus passengers in the second half of 2023 to understand changes in travel patterns and readapt the bus network to new needs [9].

2. Description of the data and cities analyzed

For this work, 5 of the most important cities in the Western Hemisphere and their metropolitan regions (RM) were selected, namely São Paulo (São Paulo Metropolitan Region - RMSP)[10], New York (*New York Metropolitan Area*)[11], Paris (*Métropole du Grand Paris - MGP*)[12], London (*London Metropolitan Area - LMA*)[13] and Mexico City (*Zona Metropolitana del Valle de México - ZMVM*)[14]. Table 1 shows the main data for these cities and their RMs.

Table 1. Data from the cities and metropolitan regions under study.

City	Area (Sq.km)	Population (inh.)	Density (inh./Sq.km)	MR	Area (Sq.km)	Population (inh.)	Density (inh./Sq.km)
São Paulo [10]	1,521.20	11,451,245	7,527.8	RMSP	7,947	20,743,587	2,610.2
New York [11]	778.18	8,804,190	11,313.8	NYMA	8,936	20,140,470	2,253.9
Paris [12]	105.40	2,148,271	20,382.1	MGP	12,011	12,140,526	1,010.8
London [13]	1,737.90	8,799,800	5,063.5	LMA	8,382	14,800,000	1,765.7
México City [14]	1,495.00	9,209,944	6,160.5	ZMVM	5,954	21,804,515	3,662.2

Data on passengers transported were obtained from transport companies or authorities in São Paulo [15, 16, 17, 18], New York [19, 20], Paris [21, 22, 23], London [24] and Mexico City [25, 26, 27].

2. Data analysis

The metro networks (Figure 1(a)) had very similar numbers before the pandemic, with a very close recovery after the pandemic, with the exception of Paris. In rail transport (Figure 1(b)), it can be seen that Paris is well above the others and Mexico City is well below, both before and after the pandemic. In the bus system (Figure 1(c)), São Paulo has higher volumes and Mexico City much lower.

Figure 2. Annual passenger volumes in subway (a), train (b) and bus systems in São Paulo, New York, Paris, London and Mexico City.

The variation in the number of passengers transported in each system, based on the year 2017, can be seen in Table 2. It was decided to start in 2017 to make it possible to verify the variation of each system before and after March 2020, a critical period at the start of the pandemic.

Table 2. Variation in the volume of passengers transported annually by the subway, rail and bus systems (percentage calculated based on 2017 value).

	São Paulo			New York			Paris			London			Mexico City		
	S ¹	T ¹	B ¹	S	T	B	S	T	B	S	T	B	S	T	B
2018	4.35	4.30	-2.72	-2.74	3.90	-4.69	2.29	-2.23	0.29	-5.40	-3.56	-7.64	2.17	1.86	3.98
2019	14.74	-15.80	-8.31	-1.71	8.25	-6.52	0.24	-2.37	0.25	-3.69	-1.25	-9.09	1.93	1.28	7.33
2020	-41.34	-49.91	-44.43	-62.98	-61.64	-47.24	-46.89	-47.37	-35.48	-64.43	-53.89	-52.28	-42.88	-47.73	-32.33
2021	-38.82	-45.88	-41.89	-56.00	-57.14	-47.12	-30.07	-34.70	-24.16	-57.50	-43.56	-46.05	-49.06	-46.59	-22.55
2022	-15.24	-28.35	-28.69	-41.33	-28.35	-41.27	-5.33	-5.30	-12.74	-30.85	-5.78	-27.56	-33.77	-27.59	7.04

¹ S = Subway System, T = Train system, B = Bus System.

In the metro system, Figure 2(a), only São Paulo was on the rise pre-pandemic and Paris has the best post-pandemic recovery, remaining 5,3% below 2017 in 2022. In the railway system, Figure 2(b), only New York was on the rise pre-pandemic and London had a better post-pandemic recovery, remaining in 2022 5,8% below 2017. In the bus system, Figure 2(c), only Mexico City was on the rise in pre-pandemic and had the best post-pandemic recovery, remaining 7,0% above 2017 in 2022.

Figure 2. Variation in the volume of passengers transported annually by the subway (a), rail (b) and bus (c) systems (based on 2017 value).

3. Discussions and Conclusions

The analysis of the data presented in this study provided a comprehensive assessment of the condition of transport systems in the capitals and metropolitan regions analyzed. It was evident that, even before the pandemic, several of these systems were already experiencing a downward trend in their operations. This phenomenon manifested itself in the subway systems of New York and London, the railway systems of São Paulo, Paris and London, as well as the bus systems of São Paulo, New York and London. The pandemic, with the abrupt cessation of travel, interrupted these logics of decline with a sharp drop in March 2020. The resumption of post-pandemic activities is gradually reestablishing flows in the various transport systems, at levels even lower than those observed before pandemic, reflecting a new reality in the transport needs of the population of these cities. It is worth reflecting here, “are societies migrating to a new way of organizing urban life, with less need for travel in urban areas and requiring less formal transport systems?” This study, until now, has not analyzed the social, cultural, economic and geopolitical issues

of these societies to answer this question, but we can infer that it may be necessary, in a few years, to rethink the entire logic of urban travel and transport provision. in cities, according to what the City of São Paulo is already doing in its urban bus system [9].

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